

Location

Zwarteweg Heerde,
Nederland

Innovation

CPIM/ BIM-Based
Element Tracking

Partners

DEMO

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

- › Geometric data (BIM models, 3D element geometry)
- › Condition and inspection data (visual checks, damage status)
- › Certification and testing data (quality assessments, compliance records)
- › Identification data (QR codes linked to unique element IDs)

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

Develop a QR-enabled BIM workflow that allows on-site identification, updating, and tracking of individual building elements, linking physical components to their digital counterparts and recording their condition, or certification. Expected results: A live, traceable BIM model where each element's status, history, and relationships are continuously updated, enabling reliable tracking throughout deconstruction and reuse.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- › **KPI 1:** Element-BIM traceability
- › **KPI 2:** Accuracy, reliability and completeness of the digital connection between QR codes and BIM objects
- › **KPI 3:** Effectiveness of IFC-based model filtering in improving spatial clarity
- › **KPI 4:** QR-code scan success rate under field conditions
- › **KPI 5:** Field user adoption rate of the Reincarnate system
- › **KPI 6:** Information retrieval time for BIM-related data via QR interface
- › **KPI 7:** Error rate in element selection and identification
- › **KPI 8:** Share of mobile-based system usage during on-site operations
- › **KPI 9:** Accessibility and completeness of documentation via QR-linked BIM data
- › **KPI 10:** Consistency between BIM model data and on-site physical reality

IMPACT

IMAGES

01. Donor building

02. Dismantling

03. Storing

04. Receiver building

CONTACTS

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